

TERRAVISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform to Enhance the life cycle of Critical Raw Materials

 TERRAVISION_EUP

 TERRAVISION EU Project

 <https://terravision-project.eu>

Project Facts

CALL: Resilient Value Chains 2023 (HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01)

TOPIC: Earth Observation platform, products and services for raw materials (HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-06)

DURATION: 48M (2024-2028) | **START DATE:** 01 January 2024

Partners

AuroraGeo Consulting
Earth Scientists and Engineers

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